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МУНДАРИЖА | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Kh.P. Kamilov, K.A. Takhirova, A.B. Saparov ROLE OF OSTEOPOROSIS IN PATHOGENESIS OF PERIODONTIUM DISEASES.....	6
2. Kh.P. Kamilov, A.A. Kadirbaeva, Sh. N. Dadamukhamedov LICHEN PLANUS OF ORAL MUCOSA CLINICS AND TREATMENT REVIEW.....	11
3. Pulatova Shakhnoza Haydarovna OPTIMIZATION OF CARDIOGENIC SHOCK TREATMENT.....	19
4. Turdiev U.M. ATHEROSCLEROTIC LESION OF THE CORONARY ARTERIES IN PATIENTS WITH EARLY DEVELOPMENT OF ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME.....	24
5. Usmanova Shoira, Fasikhiddinov Jaloliddin, Yuldashev Akrom ALGORITHM FOR PREDICTING THE PROGRESSION OF ORAL DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH TUBULOINTERSTITIAL KIDNEY DISEASE.....	30
6. Juraeva N.M., Amirkhamzaev A.T. MODERN ASPECTS OF THERAPEUTIC AND DIAGNOSTIC TACTICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STROKE (literature review).....	35
7. Ibragimova M.Kh., Nabiyeva M. FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL COURSE AND TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RECURRENT APHTHOSIS STOMATITIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN.....	42
8. Kakhkharova D.J., Alisherova Z.S., Temirova G.E., Abdulazizov T.U., Sokinjonov I.S. LEUKOPLAKIA OF THE ORAL MUCOSA: DIAGNOSTICS - THERAPY – PROGNOSIS....	46
9. Daminova Sh.B., Khasanov E.T. A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF THE RISK AND SERENCE OF DENTAL HYPERESTHESIA AFTER A WHITENING PROCEDURE.....	53

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REVIEW**
 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7259307>
ABSTRACT

This paper is review of clinical appearance of lichen planus on oral mucosa and methods of treatment. Existing complex methods of treatment help to reduce the severity of the disease, which is expressed in lengthening the terms of remission, reducing the time of epithelialization of pathological elements, reducing their number and size. To achieve stable results in the treatment of lichen planus, it is necessary to periodically repeat courses of complex therapy. The choice of optimal methods of general and local therapy should be based on an individual approach to each patient.

Keywords: oral mucosa, lichen planus, clinical forms, treatment.

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ЛЕЧЕНИЕ. ОБЗОР****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В статье представлен обзор клинических проявлений красного плоского лишая на слизистой оболочке полости рта и методов лечения. Существующие комплексные методы лечения позволяют уменьшить тяжесть заболевания, что выражается в удлинении сроков

ремиссии, сокращении сроков эпителизации патологических элементов, уменьшении их количества и размеров. Для достижения стойких результатов в лечении красного плоского лишая необходимо периодически повторять курсы комплексной терапии. Выбор оптимальных методов общей и местной терапии должен основываться на индивидуальном подходе к каждому пациенту.

Ключевые слова: слизистая оболочка полости рта, красный плоский лишай, клинические формы, лечение.

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ОҒИЗ БЎШЛИҒИ ШИЛЛИҚ ҚАВАТИНИНГ ҚИЗИЛ ЯССИ ТЕМИРАТКИ КЛИНИКАСИ ВА ДАВОЛАШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада оғиз бўшлиғи шиллиқ қаватида қизил ясси темираткининг клиник кўринишлари ва даволаш усуллари ҳақида умумий маълумот берилган. Мавжуд комплекс даволаш усуллари касалликнинг оғирлигини камайтириши мумкин, бу ремиссия муддатини узайтириш, патологик элементларнинг эпителизация вақтини қисқартириш, уларнинг сони ва ҳажмини камайтириш билан ифодалангани. Қизил ясси темираткини даволашда барқарор натижаларга еришиш учун вақти-вақти билан мураккаб терапия курсларини такрорлаш керак. Умумий ва маҳаллий терапиянинг оптимал усулларини танлаш ҳар бир беморга индивидуал ёндашувга асосланиши керак.

Калит сўзлар: оғиз шиллиқ қавати, қизил ясси темиратки, клиник шакллари, даволаш.

The term "lichen planus" was introduced by F. Gebra in 1860 [7], and in 1869 the English dermatologist E. Wilson first drew attention to the dental aspects of lichen planus (LP) and was the first to describe lesions of the oral mucosa, characteristic for this dermatosis [5]. Tibierzhe in 1885 gave a detailed description of the disease, in which he used a comparison of rashes with fern leaves that has come down to our time. In 1872, G. Koebner described an isomorphic reaction-phenomenon characterized by skin and/or mucous membrane lesions in the form of long lines in response to trauma in patients with psoriasis, eczema, and LP [4]. Louis Frederick Wickham was the first to describe the characteristic small, white or gray lines on the surface of papules, known as "Wickham's grid" [2]. In 1910, François Henri Allopeau was the first to report a case of oral mucosal cancer in LP [6]. Despite the fact that LP was described more than 150 years ago, this disease still remains an important problem in clinical dentistry. According to A.L. Mashkilleison [11], there are six clinical forms of LP of the oral mucosa and red border of the lips: typical, hyperkeratotic, exudative-hyperemic, erosive-ulcerative, bullous, and atypical. Clinical picture The main pathomorphological element in all forms of LP is a milky-white or grayish papule, but with an exudative-hyperemic form, erythema of a congestive type also occurs, with an erosive-ulcerative form - erythema, erosion or ulcer, with a bullous form - a bubble, erosion, erythema; in the hyperkeratotic form, papules coalesce into plaques [2, 7]. The favorite location of LP in the oral cavity is the distal buccal mucosa (78.5-90.0%), tongue (30.0-51.3%), mucosa of the alveolar process/gingival margin (13.0-27, 5%), the mucous membrane of the palate and the red border of the lips are affected much less frequently (1.9-9.3%). LP of the oral mucosa is characterized by the following clinical features: chronic relapsing

course, polymorphism of clinical manifestations, and the possibility of tumor transformation [6]. At the same time, malignancy of the process occurs in 1.1–6.3% of cases. There are acute and chronic stages of the disease. In the acute stage, with a typical form, new papules appear, with exudative-hyperemic, hyperemia and exudation increase, with an erosive-ulcerative form, new erosions appear or existing ones increase in size. Any injury to the mucosa can cause new lesions or worsening of symptoms (positive Koebner's sign). In the chronic stage of the disease, the Koebner symptom is negative, the process does not progress, the rashes may periodically disappear, but then reappear.

Characteristics of clinical forms of lichen planus

Typical form. On the mucous membrane of the oral cavity, grayish-white papules ranging in size from 0.2 to 2-3 mm merge into a bizarre pattern in the form of lace, mesh, fern leaves (Wickham's mesh) and are located on a pale pink (less often stagnantly hyperemic) buccal mucosa, lips, in the retromolar region, on the lateral surfaces of the tongue. The surface of the papules slightly protrudes above the level of the mucous membrane. The color of the papules is due to the keratinization of the epithelium. Plaques form on the mucous membrane of the tongue, which look like white fields ranging in size from 0.5 to 2 cm or more. In these areas, the papillae of the tongue are absent or their height is significantly reduced. Perhaps the location of the papules in the gum area parallel to their edge. In the oral cavity and on the red border of the lips, the lesions are localized, as a rule, symmetrically.

Exudative-hyperemic form. On the hyperemic mucous membrane of the cheeks, lips, floor of the mouth, lateral surfaces of the tongue, multiple gray-white papules up to 2 mm in size appear. They can be single or merge into bizarre patterns, however, against a hyperemic background, the "Wickham grid" is poorly visible. It becomes clearly visible after lubrication of the mucous membrane with a solution containing iodine, potassium iodide and water (Schiller-Pisarev test). Violations of the integrity of the epithelium are not detected.

Erosive and ulcerative form. Sharply painful erosions of various sizes, from punctate to extensive, covered with a dense fibrinous coating, against the background of a characteristic papular pattern (lace, mesh, etc.) of lichen planus, are localized on the mucous membrane of the oral cavity against a hyperemic background of irregular shape. The submandibular and submental lymph nodes are soft, mobile, and may be somewhat enlarged.

bullous form. The mucous membrane of the oral cavity in color is not changed or slightly hyperemic. Bubbles with a diameter of 5 to 20 mm with cloudy or hemorrhagic contents are visible. Multiple papules form a characteristic pattern (lace, fern leaves, etc.). Subepithelial blisters exist from several hours to several days.

hyperkeratotic form. On the mucous membrane of the oral cavity there are single areas of hyperkeratosis of various shapes and outlines, with clear boundaries, against the background of characteristic papular elements.

atypical form. The alveolar part of the gum in the area of the anterior group of teeth of the upper jaw and upper lip is hyperemic, edematous, the epithelium is thinned. Sometimes erosion occurs. Papules are grayish-white in color, barely visible. The mouths of small salivary glands on the mucous membrane of the upper lip are dilated.

Treatment The treatment of LP is a difficult task due to the fact that the etiology and pathogenesis of the disease have not been fully elucidated. Particular attention is paid to the identification of concomitant pathologies, primarily diseases of the gastrointestinal tract and liver, infectious allergies, vitamin deficiency, disorders of the central and autonomic nervous system, viral infection, etc. In the presence of such systemic disorders, therapy is prescribed in joint consultation with an internist . Currently, in the complex therapy of LP, a special place is given to the means of general exposure. The choice of therapeutic drugs is based on the need to influence different links of pathogenesis. Based on the hypothesis of the immunological mechanism of LP and its presentation as a delayed-type allergic hypersensitivity reaction, most specialists in the pathology of the oral mucosa give glucocorticoids the leading place in the treatment of severe continuously recurrent forms of the disease [8]. The drugs of this group have anti-inflammatory, immunosuppressive and hyposensitizing effects. For a long time in Russia, in the treatment of LP, schemes with the use of systemic glucocorticoids, mainly prednisolone, hydrocortisone, dexamethasone, triamcinolone (polcortolone), that is, drugs with relatively low therapeutic activity and a wide range of complications and side effects, have been used [10]. There is information [1] about the use of glucocorticoids in the form of injections under the elements of mucosal lesions in cases of severe persistent LP. The authors point to a reduction in the resolution and epithelization of erosive and

ulcerative elements, the achievement of therapeutic efficacy in 68.0-75.0% of patients. However, an unfavorable consequence of the use of this method is often coarse scarring of the mucous membrane at the injection site. In addition, injection administration of the drug may cause the same side effects as with oral use of glucocorticoids [3]. Limitations of local injection of glucocorticoids are associated with its morbidity. Along with the therapeutic effect, glucocorticoids are characterized by pronounced side effects associated with their influence on all types of metabolism - protein, carbohydrate, fat and water-electrolyte, which often limits their use. Foreign literature provides convincing evidence of the expediency of using certain groups of topical steroids in the treatment of erosive-ulcerative, vesiculo-bullous lesions of the oral mucosa, including LP. Many of these severe forms of the disease are successfully treated with highly active topical steroids, which have high clinical activity and minimal side effects compared to systemic glucocorticoids. According to American and European researchers, seven classes of topical glucocorticoid drugs are distinguished depending on the degree of their anti-inflammatory activity: from 1st (drugs of maximum potency) to 7th (drugs of minimal potency) [9]. In modern foreign dental practice, clobetasol (clobetasol propionate) is one of the most frequently and reasonably used topical steroids in the treatment of LP [4]. An important mechanism of action of clobetasol is the induction of vasoconstriction, followed by a decrease in inflammation due to a decrease in the level of histamine, as well as the effects of catecholamines in the peripheral bloodstream. It is these convincing evidence of the high efficiency of topical use of highly active clobetasol that made it possible to revise the position of the World Health Organization on the prescription of systemic glucocorticoids in the treatment of severe destructive forms of lesions of the oral mucosa [6]. Prolonged use of topical steroids can provoke the development of dysbiosis in the oral cavity, manifested as a candidal infection [8]. For this reason, in patients treated with topical glucocorticoids for a long time, in order to avoid the development and progression of dysbiotic conditions of the oral cavity, it is recommended to simultaneously prescribe local antifungal therapy [8]. Topical calcineurin inhibitors are a new class of drugs that, while being as effective as strong hormonal drugs, are devoid of the side effects described above. T.V. Libik (2010) and many foreign experts revealed the high efficiency of the use of local anti-inflammatory drugs based on calcineurin inhibitors (1% pimecrolimus, 0.1% tacrolimus), which, since 2004, have been widely (according to indications) used abroad in a complex therapy for destructive forms of LP [7]. According to experts, the effectiveness of topical application of 1% pimecrolimus in the treatment of patients with LP is associated with a powerful and versatile anti-inflammatory effect: pimecrolimus selectively inhibits the synthesis and release of cytokines and inflammatory mediators from T-lymphocytes and mast cells, specifically binds to the cytosolic receptor macrophilin-12 and inhibits calcium-dependent phosphatase - calcineurin. It has also been established that inhibition of calcineurin leads to suppression of T-lymphocyte proliferation and prevents transcription and synthesis of early cytokines in T-helpers of the 1st and 2nd types, such as interleukin-2, interferon γ , interleukin-4, interleukin-5, interleukin-10, tumor necrosis factor alpha and granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor. Most researchers [4] indicate the need for long-term (at least a month) therapy with calcineurin inhibitors to exclude recurrences of erosive and ulcerative lesions. It is also reported that patients may experience a mild, rapidly passing paresthetic symptom at the initial stages of treatment with 1% pimecrolimus [6]. Cyclosporine is an immunosuppressant, a cyclic polypeptide consisting of 11 amino acids. In LP, the use of cyclosporine A in the form of mouth rinses or adhesive paste with cyclosporine A is effective. Side effects may include gingival hyperplasia, which disappears after discontinuation of the drug [7]. Tacrolimus is an immunosuppressive drug belonging to the group of natural macrolides. It is produced by the actinomycete *Streptomyces tsukubaensis*. Tacrolimus is similar in immunosuppressive effects to cyclosporine, but is more active and effective at lower doses, has a greater ability to penetrate into the mucous membrane. With LP, it is used topically for rinsing the mouth. The treatment is carried out until the condition improves, approximately within 14 days, then a 3-4 week break is taken, after which the treatment is continued again. Retinoids - derivatives of vitamin A (etretinate), reduce the intensity of the inflammatory response, affect the state of cell membranes and normalize proliferation processes. In recent years, vitamin A analogues, carotenoids (Fenoro preparation), have been successfully used, especially in atypical forms of LP, in particular,

erosive and ulcerative, as well as in lesions of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity and genital organs [8]. The action of lower doses of retinoids in combination with other antioxidant agents such as vitamin E (α -tocopherol acetate) is known to be enhanced [4]. The multivitamin preparation aevit is indicated for patients with a long chronic course of the disease, verrucous forms and lesions of the mucous membranes. In addition, vitamin E, used as an antioxidant and inhibitor of the cytochrome P450 system, makes it possible to reduce the daily dose and reduce the duration of steroid therapy in the complex treatment with glucocorticoids. In the chronic recurrent course of dermatosis, agents that improve oxygen supply to tissues, such as cytochrome C (cyto-mac), actovegin, are indicated. In the complex of treatment of patients with LP, according to many experts, taking into account the role of allergenic factors, a certain place is given to hyposensitizing therapy. Recommend the use of third-generation antihistamines that do not cause a sedative effect: loratadine (Claritin), cetirizine (Zyrtec), diprazine, desloratadine (Erius), fexofenadine (Telfast) [10]. For many years, histamine + normal human immunoglobulin (hystaglobulin) has been successfully used in the treatment of LP, under the influence of which antihistamine antibodies are synthesized in the human body and the ability of blood serum to inactivate free histamine increases. Given the fact that LP most often develops as a cell-mediated type of allergic reaction, it is advisable to use 4-aminoquinoline derivatives known as antimalarial drugs (chloroquine, hydroxychloroquine) in the treatment of patients [5]. These drugs inhibit the autoimmune process, are weak cytostatics, inhibit the functions of macrophages, which stops autocytolysis. Unfortunately, the effect of this treatment develops slowly, after 1-3 months of continuous treatment. Dentists note that the main advantage of aminoquinoline preparations is their good tolerability. An infrequent but most serious side effect is the possibility of the drug (chloroquine) being deposited in the cornea and retina, which is manifested by diplopia, a sensation of spots or dots before the eyes. This side effect is reversible, it practically does not lead to persistent visual impairment with timely cancellation, however, it reduces the quality of life of patients. It is known that microcirculatory disorders play a significant role in the pathogenesis of LP [2], and therefore, direct anticoagulants are recommended to normalize microcirculatory disorders in LP patients suffering from cardiovascular pathology. Low doses of heparin analogues have an antiproliferative and immunomodulatory effect. Good results in generalized forms of LP of the oral mucosa were obtained with subcutaneous administration of low doses of enoxaparin sodium (low molecular weight heparin). Vascular agents remain an important component in the treatment of all forms of LP of the oral mucosa. They help to improve blood supply and normalize the permeability of the vascular wall, which leads to the resorption of papular elements and accelerates the epithelization of erosions. Niacin preparations (niacin, nicotinamide, etc.) are still used both in local and general therapy of LP [2]. Vitamin PP causes activation of fibrinolysis, has a vasodilating effect, has a wide spectrum of action on blood lipids and lipoproteins and can be useful in the complex treatment of patients with LP. In the treatment of various forms of LP, xanthinol nicotinate, which combines the properties of substances from the theophylline group and nicotinic acid, has proven itself well. The drug has a vasodilating and antiaggregatory effect, interacts with adenosine receptors, blocks phosphodiesterase, increases the formation of cyclic adenosine monophosphate, reduces the calcium content in smooth muscles, dilates blood vessels, which pathogenetically predetermines the feasibility of its use in the treatment of patients with LP. Supporters of the infectious theory believe that the first step in the treatment of LP should be antibiotic therapy. According to A.L. Mashkilleyson et al. (1995), in the treatment of antibiotics, first of all, sanitation of the body is achieved. A favorable effect in LP is given by treatment with broad-spectrum antibiotics: tetracyclines, macrolides. In domestic practice, the antiprotozoal drug metronidazole is successfully used to treat erosive and ulcerative forms of LP. Given the possible role of viruses in the etiology of LP, some authors [10] consider it expedient to include antiviral drugs in the complex treatment of LP. In the presence of concomitant candidal infection, antifungal drugs are used: fluconazole, ketoconazole [4], miconazole [4], etc. Against the background of the use of antifungal drugs in patients with erosive and ulcerative form of LP of the oral mucosa, a decrease in inflammation and an acceleration of epithelialization of lesions are noted. In the studies of I.V. Bezrukova (1997) and L.V. Petrova (2002) found the presence of dysbiotic changes and dysbacteriosis in patients with LP of the oral mucosa, which justifies the need

to include drugs that normalize the microflora in the complex therapy of the disease: normase, lysozyme-containing drug bifiliz, lactusan and lactose-containing probiotics, eubiotics bifidumbacterin, bifidumbacterin forte, lactobacterin, linex, bifikol [5]. The close connection of LP with the pathology of the gastrointestinal tract justifies the inclusion in the complex of therapeutic measures of agents that affect the speed and completeness of parietal digestion and absorption of carbohydrates in the intestine, such as festal, colibacterin, choleric herbs, and tykveol [3]. In order to adsorb toxic substances, products of incomplete metabolism, allergens from the intestines, remove pathological microflora, enterosorbents are introduced into the treatment regimen: chitosan, ensoral. Due to the fact that the material basis of LP is immune inflammation, including the occurrence of a delayed-type hypersensitivity reaction, the correction of disorders of local and general immunity in patients with LP is of particular importance. The most widely used substances of endogenous origin, in particular thymus extracts: thymalin, thymogen, imunofan, taktivin. In the context of the choice of treatment methods for LP, it is important that, in addition to the immunomodulatory effect, thymus extracts stimulate regeneration processes. According to A.V. Shumsky [2], when LP is combined with a viral or microbial infection, the drug imunofan is most effective. A positive clinical and laboratory effect of lycopid in the treatment of LP was demonstrated [6]. The use of lycopide in the complex treatment of LP can increase the antibacterial, antifungal and antiviral effect of the appropriate therapy. Since 1995, dental practice has begun to use imudon, a preparation consisting of a mixture of lysates of various microorganisms, which has specific and nonspecific immunotropic effects, which increases the content of lysozyme in saliva, stimulates the synthesis of antibodies and the phagocytic activity of macrophages [5]. In severe forms of LP or in combination with somatic pathology, a new domestic drug of complex action, azoxymer bromide (polyoxidonium), has proven itself well, which is used as an immunomodulator, detoxifier, and prolonging carrier of many pharmacologically active compounds [6]. According to researchers [7], azoximer bromide (polyoxidonium) is an indispensable drug in the general treatment of LP due to its antioxidant and membrane-stabilizing effect. Given the important role of stress in the pathogenesis of LP, sedatives are included in the complex treatment: valerian root (infusion, tincture, extract), corvalol or valocordin, motherwort herb, nutraceutical preparations and their combinations (persen-forte, novopassit, peony tincture), tranquilizers [chlordiazepoxide (Elenium), diazepam (Sibazon)], and if you are prone to depression, drugs with a mild antidepressant effect are recommended [St. In the complex treatment of LP, it is advisable to prescribe B vitamins. The use of multivitamin preparations (pentovit, pentahexavit, aevit, etc.) is especially indicated during the period of LP remission. It is considered appropriate for patients with LP to prescribe multivitamins containing trace elements with an increased dose of vitamins of group B, PP, A, E (panhexavit, undevit, multitabs, centrum). An important place in the treatment of LP is given to diet - the exclusion of spicy, spicy, rough foods, strong alcoholic drinks and smoking. One of the links in complex therapy is local treatment. First of all, it is the sanitation of the oral cavity, the elimination of traumatic factors and foci of chronic infection, the use of painkillers, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and keratoplastic agents. Since the appearance of erosions and ulcers is accompanied by a pronounced pain syndrome, which leads to a violation of the patient's quality of life, an important component of local treatment is pain relief. A good analgesic effect is achieved with the use of local anesthetics - tetracaine, pyromecaine. Oil solutions, a suspension of anesthesin in glycerol, and liquid oils (peach, apricot, and olive) are also used. In order to epithelize the elements of the lesion, applications of oil solutions of vitamins A and E, 5-10% methyluracil ointment, carotene, sea buckthorn oil, rosehip oil, solcoseryl in the form of jelly, ointment, and dental adhesive paste in the form of applications on problem areas of the oral mucosa are used. mouth. Under the action of solcoseryl, spasm of arteries and arterioles decreases, new collateral vessels grow, tissue trophism improves, fibroblast proliferation and migration increase, and collagen synthesis increases. This dosage form also has an analgesic effect. Due to its properties, the drug is adhesively fixed to the oral mucosa, providing a prolonged therapeutic effect [18 , 37]. In order to correct microcirculation disorders, applications of 1% galascorbin solution, 5% solution of aminocaproic acid, applications of heparin, troxevasin, actovegin ointments are used. In erosive-ulcerative and bullous forms of LP, ointments based on glucocorticoids are used to stop the process

in the form of applications to problem areas of the mucous membrane . In the local treatment of LP of the oral mucosa, drugs are used in the form of films. In the studies of A.A. Epishova (1993), L.V. Petrova (2002), E.G. Epimakhova (2005), M. Battino et al. (2008) established an increase in lipid peroxidation processes and a deficiency of antioxidant protection in LP of the oral mucosa, which justifies the inclusion of antioxidants in the treatment regimen. Antioxidant drugs that normalize the state of cell membranes significantly improve the prognosis of any clinical form of LP of the oral mucosa. T.I. Lemetskaya et al. (2002) proposed an alternative method for the treatment of LP of the oral mucosa with complex homeopathic preparations in the form of injections under the lesions [9]. Currently, photodynamic therapy, photochemotherapy (PUVA) [9], and laser therapy are successfully used. The complex treatment of LP of the oral mucosa also includes physiotherapeutic methods. Thus, there is currently no generally accepted treatment for LP leading to a complete cure. Existing complex methods of treatment help to reduce the severity of the disease, which is expressed in lengthening the terms of remission, reducing the time of epithelialization of pathological elements, reducing their number and size. To achieve stable results in the treatment of LP, it is necessary to periodically repeat courses of complex therapy. The choice of optimal methods of general and local therapy should be based on an individual approach to each patient.

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